

INITIAL VIEWS OF THE JADIDS ON EDUCATION

Juliboyev Alimardon Abdulmajidovich

The student of the Kokand SPI, History faculty

Annotation: In this article, the views of the first manifestations of the Jadidism movement in the education and educational system and their ideas, attention is paid to science as a special field, information about the ability to use the experience of foreign countries in its place. cited. For example, what kind of attention is paid to education in the countries of the world, what was it like in our country, the fact that they analyzed their achievements and shortcomings and worked hard for the development of this field, why is it necessary for us to introduce "new method" schools? We think about it.

Keywords: Education, development, science, "modern method", special program, culture, language.

On August 23, 2019, the Honorable President Shavkat Mirziyoyev made the following comments at the video meeting "Dedicated to the issues of developing the public education system, increasing the qualifications and influence of pedagogues in society, and raising the morale of young people": "Developed in the world if we look at the history of the countries, we see that all the reforms in them started from the preschool education system, that is, from kindergarten, school, education. Because without changing the school, you cannot change a person, society. That is why our great-grandfathers of the last century put the issue of school in the first place. There is a deep meaning in the words of the great educator Mahmudhoja Behbudi: "The greatest building in the world is a school." And we, being in love with our colleges, which are shiny on the surface and shaky on the inside, wasted so much time. Even in the recent past, our fathers, brothers, and sisters did not study in very luxurious schools. However, their knowledge, skills, and pride were high, and they were not indifferent to the fate

of the country”⁵. After the independence of our country, in all aspects of social and political life, great things are being done in the realization of identity, deep understanding and conveying of spiritual and educational values to the people, education of young people in the spirit of love for the country and the people. The government is developing special programs for the development of spiritual life. Special attention is paid to the education and training of talented young people, the necessary conditions for their education abroad. The enlighteners of Jadid also considered the education of young people as a matter of life or death.

Far-seeing intellectuals and thinkers began to express critical thoughts about the stagnation of the educational system in our country, which is completely disconnected from the world development, in the beginning of the 19th century. The accomplished historian, scientist, writer, philanthropist, the great Uzbek poet, statesman Nodirabegim, the son of Hakim Khan Tora Masumkhan Tora, was in the Russian cities of Semipalatinsk (Shamay), Omsk, Orenburg, and Astrakhan. , in which the attitude of the khanates to the state, education and training system changed dramatically, and he realized how far behind the country was from development. The thinker, who was fluent in Russian as well as Eastern languages, was closely acquainted with the Russian state and education system, and the fact that special educational institutions and boarding houses were opened for orphans who were left without fathers and mothers in the cities there, and that they were educated at the expense of the state. it was news⁶. In 1826, Hakim Khan left Russia and visited Muslim countries such as Turkey and Egypt. In Egypt, he meets Muhammadali Pasha, gets to know his reforming activities closely. He was surprised that the Pasha of Muhammadali sent 40 young Turkish men to study in Europe for 7 years to acquire various knowledge. It is worth noting that it is appropriate to entrust the responsible task of leading these forty young men to Europe to Hakim Khan. But due to his return to his homeland, he will not be able to undertake this task. Hakim Khan thoroughly studies the new schools established by Pasha Muhammadali, where worldly sciences are taught. The selection of students for schools

⁵ Mirziyoyev Sh. M. Milliy tiklanishdan – milliy yuksalish sari. 4 – jild . – T.: O‘zbekiston nashriyoti, 2020. [B, 143 – 144]

⁶ Dolimov U. Turkistonda jadid maktablari. – T.: Universitet nashriyoti, 2006. [B, 8]

and various fields of study, the subjects to be taught, especially the provision of jobs suitable to the talents of the graduates, are covered in detail in the work "Muntakhab ut-tavorex": "There are various learned teachers and khatib to teach them. After all, one group of Arabs and one group of Persians and one group of Turks and one group of Favji farangs and one group were practicing. And after mastering these sciences, they give privileges and exams. If there is any kind of education, they will separate it. As much as he has every month, Muhamadali takes it to the pasha services. He manages his talent and knowledge for a service. One group of young men is sent to the courthouse, until they can benefit from the science of medicine, and they send a group to Farangistan, so that they come to know the western sciences, and theirs has not benefited from the knowledge, until the education has not made a mark, and it is separated. , they send him to jihad, he becomes a soldier. At the end of every month, the rule is overturned"⁷.

The intellectuals of Turkestan took jadidism (Arabic jadid - "new") as the basis for their patriotic activities. It has become the general name of the environment and ideological direction that was born among progressive national intellectuals. This ideological outlook became the main ideological movement and social thought against subjugation and slavery among the Muslim peoples of the Crimea, Volgaboyi, Caucasus and Turkestan at the end of the 19th century and the first quarter of the 20th century. Its supporters strived to create new, modern forms of education and national development. The most serious and valuable resource of any land, country, nation and region is not oil, gas or gold, but people, intelligent and intelligent citizens. History shows that the availability of raw materials and natural resources does not change anything and does not guarantee the development of nations. It is because of this that at the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century, Turkestan moderns considered it their national duty to find new ways of education, to open the first university, and to send talented young people to study in Europe. Because only intelligent, knowledgeable people can achieve personal freedom, respect for human

⁷ O'sha kitob. [B, 8 – 9]

rights, freedom of speech and thought, and create a developed legal state⁸. The first modern schools were opened in 1898 in the city of Kokan by teacher Salahiddin. In 1899, this work was continued by Mannon Qori in Tashkent and Shamsiddin Domla in Andijan. By 1911, the total number of new method schools in Turkestan was 63, 4106 students studied in them; 30 schools were operating in Fergana region, 12 in Yettisuv, 5 in Samarkand. Tashkent, of course, was distinguished by the number of schools (their number was 24) and the quality of education⁹. Schools based on "Usuli Savtiya" (sound method) named "Method Jadid" were created against "Rus-tuzem" schools with attention to essence. In the "Usuli Jadid" schools, the first priority is to educate young people with high morale, who are passionate about the future of the nation and the Motherland. The great merits of Jadid pedagogues is that they considered education in their mother tongue, national literature, teaching the basics of the Muslim religion as a crucial issue. Because they considered the mother tongue and national literature to be the main means of preserving the nation's identity¹⁰. At this point, it is appropriate to dwell on the activities of Ismailbey Gaspirali, who spread the modern schools of the method in Turkestan. Ismailbey Gaspirali's "Tarjiman" newspaper was interested in the economic and political conditions of the Turkic peoples living under the Russian Empire. Ismailbey Gaspirali wrote in an article: "My dear friends, the most beautiful work for us is the work of knowledge and education. The most holy aspiration is the aspiration to knowledge and education. Because it is work and knowledge that make a person a person. Knowledge is a means of reaching the civilization of cultural life. "Cultural life is the purpose and method of human existence." Ismailbey Gaspirali, in an interview with the Turkish newspaper "Tasviri Avkor", openly stated why he views education as a primary issue: "Regardless of the nationality of the ruler and the convict, believe that education is the only way to keep him healthy. Provide it with the most perfect port. Put the latest progress in his hands. That nation will not and cannot benefit from it. On the contrary, such elements in that country use elements other than civilization, and the nation deprived of education will be exposed to even more poverty

⁸ Salomov Sh. N. G'oyalar janggi. – T.: Toshkent "Istiqlol" nashriyoti, 2017. [B,62 – 63]

⁹ Alimova D. Jadidchilik fenomeni. – T.: Akademnashr, 2022. [B, 11]

¹⁰ Dolimov U. Turkistonda jadid maktablari. – T.: Universitet nashriyoti, 2006. [B, 23]

and error than before. Provide this nation with the best and latest military equipment, without education, it will not be of any use. Education is necessary before everything, in a country, a school is absolutely necessary before railway, bank, road administration. Even the school is above everything else and so sacred that nothing can be compared to it. Otherwise, the destruction and destruction of the nation is inevitable." Ismailbey Gaspirali, in his book "Russian Islam", published in 1881, put on the agenda the project of fundamental reform of the education system of the Turkic peoples under the Russian Empire, including the peoples of Turkestan. It was a great revolution in the thinking of Turkic peoples.

In conclusion, we can say that these works of the progressives were very difficult from the point of view of this era, but the moderns started to implement these works together. Pedagogical work is the hardest and most honorable profession, there is probably no greater work than it. The work and hardships of these people, who paid special attention to education and expanded the activity of modern schools, will never be forgotten by their ancestors. We emphasize once again that the crisis and decline, development and prospects of any country in the world are clearly visible in its attitude to education and especially to teachers and pedagogues.

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